

IN VITRO HIV-1 RT INHIBITORY ACTIVITY OF *MADHUCA INDICA* INNER BARK EXTRACTS

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ABSTRACT

Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) infection continues to spread throughout the world despite a downward trend of HIV new infections. The study was undertaken to investigate the HIV-RT inhibitory activity of inner bark extracts of *Madhuca indica*. Sequential maceration method was performed for preparation of extracts using hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol solvents. RetroSys HIV-1 RT (Innovagen, Sweden) kit was used to determine the HIV-RT inhibitory activity of all solvents extracts. All extracts showed significant inhibitory activity. Acetone, hexane and ethyl acetate extracts shows highest inhibition of recombinant HIV-RT (88.6%, 88.1% and 81.56% respectively) at 2 and mg/ml concentration. These results were remarkable and can be used to develop a new drug for HIV treatment or other infectious diseases caused by the pathogenic micro-organisms.

Key words: HIV-1, Reverse transcriptase, *Madhuca indica*, Inner bark.

INTRODUCTION

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) causes Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS) that affects the human immune system. There were 35.3 million people living with HIV (UNAIDS, 2013). According WHO antiretroviral therapy (ART) is a treatment for people infected with HIV using anti-HIV drugs. The standard treatment consists of a combination of at least three drugs (often called “highly active antiretroviral therapy” or HAART) that suppress HIV replication. Adamson and Freed (2010) reported that drug toxicity, drug resistance, adverse drug–drug interactions, and accompanying poor patient adherence are still the major factors leading to treatment failure. Therefore, the discovery of novel drugs with new process of action, low toxicity, high activity

and well sustainable is still a challenging issue in HIV treatment. Medicinal plants play an important role in supporting healthcare system in the World. Nowadays, a large variety of natural products from medicinal plants, such as alkaloids, phytosterols, flavonoids, lignans, polysaccharides and so on, have been found to inhibit unique enzymes and proteins crucial to the life cycle of HIV, including the reverse transcription process, virus entry, the integrase or protease (Cos *et al.*, 2004; De Clercq, 2000; Venkanna and Estari, 2012).

Plants have a great potential for producing new drugs for human benefit. There is a continuous development of resistant strains which pose the need for search and development of new drug to cure diseases (Silver, 1993). Medicinal plants are finding use as pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals,

cosmetics and food supplements. Even as traditional source of medicines and they continue to play pivotal role (Swati Sharma *et al.*, 2010). Screening of potential anti-HIV agents from medicinal plants may be a rapid and effective way for drug discovery (Sainath and Estari, 2014). Bennerman (1993) reported that the use of herbal medicine is increasingly becoming more popular in many countries. Over the past decade, herbal medicines have been accepted universally, and they have an impact on both World health and international trade (Vinatha and Estari, 2013).

Several studies have described the inhibitory properties of medicinal plants on different targets in the life cycle of HIV (Vlietnick *et al.*, 1998 and Estari *et al.*, 2012). Hence, the development of drugs and medicinal agents from plants are necessary in the investigation, prevention and treatment of infectious diseases. With this background and based on previous research work (Rajendra Prasad and Estari, 2013) the *Madhuca indica* inner bark was selected for HIV-RT inhibition activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant collection:

Plant was selected for this study is based on its traditional medicinal use (Rajendra Prasad and Estari, 2012). Inner bark of *Madhuca indica* was collected from the Chintur mandal, Khammam district of Andhra Pradesh, India, in the month of September 2012. The plant voucher specimen identification was done with the help of taxonomist Prof. Vastsavaya. S. Raju, Department of Botany Kakatiya University, Warangal and the same was deposited at Infectious Diseases & Metabolic Disorders Research Lab, Department of Zoology, Kakatiya University, Warangal.

Preparation of plant extract:

After collection of selected medicinal plant material sample was dried at room temperature until they were free from moisture. The selected part of plant subjected to size reduction to get

coarse powder was then stored in a clean dry air tight container. The air dried powder was subjected to sequential maceration method used by different solvents (hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone, and methanol etc.,) for seven days. The extract was filtered mass was obtained and it was finally dried at low room temperature under pressure in a rotary vacuum evaporator (Thermotech, buchi type model th-012).

HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase Inhibition Assay:

The HIV reverse transcriptase enzyme inhibition due to each extract was determined using HIV RT inhibition assay by using of Retro Sys HIV-1 RT activity kit (Innovagen, Sweden). To determining RT activity on inhibiting substances that are to be analysed are serially diluted. The diluted substances are then added to a plate with reaction mixture. After 30 minutes of pre-incubation at 33°C, the reaction is started by the addition of a standardised amount of RT. The RT will now incorporate BrdUMP depending on the level of inhibition. The product is quantified by the addition of the RT Product Tracer which binds to the incorporated BrdUMP. After removing excess tracer the amount of bound tracer is determined by an alkaline phosphatase/pNPP colour reaction (Gronowitz *et al.*, 1992).

After correction for background signal, the measured residual RT activity for each substance dilution is calculated as a percentage of the measured RT activity in absence of inhibiting substances. Plot the percentage of residual RT activity against the concentrations of the substance dilutions for each of the tested substances. AZT (Azidothymidine) was used as control. The inhibitory effect of each substance is expressed by RT activity and is determined with the aid of the obtained graph. The percentage inhibition of HIV-1 RT was calculates as,

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{\text{A control} - \text{A sample}}{\text{A control}} \times 100.$$

Where, A is Optical Density (OD).

Table 1: Extractive values of different extracts of *Madhuca indica* inner bark

S.No	Solvent	Color of extract	Yield of the extract (in gm)	Percentage yield(% w/w)
1	Hexane	Dark red	7.1	3.55%
2	Chloroform	Dark red	6.38	3.19%
3	Ethyl acetate	Brown	6.05	3.03%
4	Acetone	Dark red	4.93	2.47%
5	Methanol	Dark red	6.48	3.24%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Percentage of yield extract:

The yield of sequential extracts of *Madhuca indica* (g) is shown in (Table 1). The amount obtained from hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol extracts are 7.100 gm, 6.380 gm, 6.050 gm, 4.930 gm, and 6.480 gm respectively.

Anti-HIV activity of *Madhuca indica* inner bark extracts:

Inhibition of HIV-RT by *Madhuca indica* inner bark extracts were presented in Figure 1. Acetone and hexane shows highest inhibition of recombinant HIV-RT (88.6% and 88.1% respectively) at 2 mg/ml concentration. Ethyl acetate, methanol and chloroform extracts shows highest inhibition of HIV-RT at 2 mg/ml concentration (81.56%, 75.7% and 73.2% respectively). While control drug (AZT) showing 91.7% at 2mg/ml concentration.

Currently many research groups are exploring the biodiversity of the plant kingdom to find anti-HIV drugs with novel process of action. Research on plant antiviral products is supported by the increasing amount of reports and publications on plant derived substances with against HIV (Maes, 2004).

A number of natural products, mainly from plants have been shown to possess anti HIV activity (Cragg and Newman, 2003 and Estari *et al.*, 2011). In the present study, the assay was optimized and standardized with respect to various experimental parameters and then applied to test the HIV-RT inhibitory activity of the different extracts.

Figure-1. HIV-1 RT inhibitory activity of *Madhuca indica* Inner bark extracts

MIHE - *Madhuca indica* hexane extract
MIAE - *Madhuca indica* acetone extract
MICE - *Madhuca indica* chloroform extract
MIME - *Madhuca indica* methanol extract
MIEAE - *Madhuca indica* ethyl acetate extract
AZT - Azidothymine

At the concentration of 0.5 mg/ml to 2 mg/ml all extractions at different concentrations shows significant inhibition of recombinant HIV-RT. The results obtained in the present investigation indicated that *Madhuca indica* inner bark with acetone and hexane extractions shows highest inhibition activity 88.6% and 88.1% at 2mg/ml against HIV-RT when compared to other extractions, while control drug (AZT) shows 91.7% at 2mg/ml concentration. The other remaining extractions ethyl acetate, methanol and chloroform extracts shows HIV-1RT inhibition at 2 mg/ml concentration (81.56%, 75.70% and 73.21% respectively).

CONCLUSION

The results obtained in the present investigation indicated *Madhuca indica* inner bark can provide lead molecules which could be useful substrate for the synthesis of new broad spectrum antibiotics for the treatment of infections caused by the pathogenic micro-organisms. Further purification, identification and characterization of the active compounds will be very important in future.

REFERENCES

1. **Adamson, C.S. Freed, E.O.** 2010. Novel approaches to inhibiting HIV-1 replication. *Antiviral Res.* 85: 119–141.
2. **Bannerman, R.** 1993. *Traditional Medicine and Healthcare.* Geneva. WHO.
3. **Cos, P. Maes, L. Vanden Berghe, D. Hermans, N. Pieters, L. and Vlietinck, A.** 2004. Plant substances as anti-HIV agents selected according to their putative mechanism of action. *J. Nat. Prod.* 67: 284–293.
4. **Cragg, G. and Newman, D.** 2003. Plants as a source of anti-cancer and anti-HIV agents. *Annals of applied biology.* 143: 127-133.
5. **De Clercq, E.** 2000. Current lead natural products for the chemotherapy of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection. *Med. Res.Rev.* 20: 323–349.
6. **Estari, M. Venkanna, L. Prasad, P. Rajendra Chary, V. Stheesh Kumar, P. and Rajendra Prasad, G.** 2012. Studies on anti HIV activity of extracts from *Eclipta alba* (L). *Diversity and Physiological Process.* 101-109.
7. **Gronowitz, J.S. Lennerstrand, J. Pettersson, A. Neumuller, M. Johansson, M. and Kallander, C.F.R.** 1992. Determination of IC50 values and mechanism of action of HIV1 RT, inhibitors, by the use of carrier bound template-primer, template, or primer, with 125I-UTP as substrate. *Antiviral Chemistry and Chemotherapy.* 3: 203-213.
8. **Silver, L.L. and Bostian, K.A.** 1993. Discovery and development of new antibiotics: the problem of antibiotic resistance. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 37(3): 377-383.
9. **Estari, M. Prasad, P. Rajendra chary, V. Satheesh, P. Rajendra Prasad, G. Venkanna, L. and Srinivas Reddy, A.** 2011. *In vitro* study for HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitory activity in extracts from *Tinospora cordifolia*. *Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences.* 30(2): 49-53
10. **Maes, P.C.** (2004). Plant substances as anti-HIV agents selected according to their putative mechanism of action. *Journal of Natural Products.* 267: 284-293.
11. **Rajendra Prasad, Gujjeti. and Estari, Mamidala.** 2013. Phytochemical Analysis and TLC Profile of *Madhuca indica* Inner Bark Plant Extract. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research.* 4(10): 1507-1510.
12. **Rajendra Prasad, Gujjeti. and Estari, Mamidala.** 2012. Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used by the tribes of Khammam district, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Journal of Research in Plant Sciences.* 1(2): 132-137.
13. **Sainath, Namthabad. Estari, Mamidala.** 2014. Molecular Docking of HIV-1 Protease using Alkaloids from *Tinospora cordifolia*. *International Journal of Research and Applications* 1(1):P12-16.
14. **Swati Sharma. Rekha Vijayvergia. and Singh, T.**2010. Evaluation of antimicrobial efficacy of some medicinal plants *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.* 2(1): 121-124.
15. **UNAIDS,** 2013. Report on the global AIDS epidemic.
16. **Vinatha, Naini. and Estari, Mamidala.** 2013. An Ethnobotanical Study of Plants for the Treatment of Diabetes in the Warangal district, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Biolife.* 1(1): 24-28.
17. **Venkanna, Lunavath and Estari.** 2012. Inhibition of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV-1) Reverse Transcriptase by *Casia occidentalis* (L) Plant Extract. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research.* 3(7): 1-4.

18. **Vleitenick, A.J. De Bruyne, T. Apers, S. Pieters, L.A.** 1998. Plant derived leading compounds for chemotherapy of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection. *Planta Medica*. 64: 97-109.
19. **WHO**, 2002. Traditional medicine strategy launched.

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